

EXPERIMENTAL FORMABILITY STUDY OF STEEL-POLYMER SANDWICH COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Steel-polymer composites are being exploited in the automotive, aerospace and construction industries due to their lower density, high specific flexural stiffness, and high vibration damping. In order to shape steel-polymer composites into products, first the formability of steel-polymer composites should be investigated. Forming limit diagram (FLD) of steel-polymer composites based on the fracture of lower steel skin has been investigated by many researchers. However, the delamination between steel and polymer is a fatal weakness in the performance of steel-polymer composites. In this study we carried out on building FLD considering various failure modes including the delamination of steel-polymer composites. Acoustic emission method was used to build FLD considering the delamination. Critical peak frequency bands that can differentiate the fracture modes were determined from various tests. These peak frequency bands enabled real time fracture during the formability test to be detected successfully.

1 INTRODUCTION

Steel-polymer composites are widely used in the automotive, aerospace and construction industries due to their low density, high specific flexural stiffness, and high vibration damping [1, 2]. In order to transform steel-polymer composites into final products, first they should be shaped. Therefore, the formability of steel-polymer composites is very important issue. One of the common methods for characterizing the formability of sheet metal is the construction of the forming limit diagram (FLD). FLD of metal usually focuses on the localized necking. As such, researchers have investigated FLD of steel-polymer composites based on the localized necking of lower steel skin [3]. On the other hand, numerical simulations have been conducted based on the failure of metal sheet [4]. However, the formability characteristic of steel-polymer composites is more complicated because it consists of materials with different mechanical properties. Furthermore, the interface between the skin and core is a fatal weakness in the performance of steel-polymer composites [5]. Therefore, experimental tool considering interfacial failure should be investigated. Few studies have been carried out on building FLD considering the delamination of steel-polymer composites.

Acoustic emission (AE) technique is widely used for structural health-monitoring system to detect real time damage of materials. Wave induced by elastic energy when material damages is observed by AE sensor. Many researches have been conducted to classify various failure modes by observing AE signal features: amplitude, rise time, and peak frequency [6].

In this study, AE signal features were investigated depending on three failure modes of steel-polymer composites: steel failure, polymer failure and delamination. According to the AE signal features, a punch test of steel-polymer composites was conducted using Nakazima method. During the punch test, in-situ AE signals were obtained, from which it was determined whether the steel-polymer composites fails or not. Finally, FLD based on the local necking and delamination was obtained that can design the shaping process of steel-polymer composites.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Sandwich sheet preparation

Steel-polymer composites consist of two steel skins and a polymer core. Electro galvanized (EG) steel was obtained from POSCO (Korea) and used as skin material. Polyamide-6 (PA6) polymer core from Goodfellow (USA) was used as the core. The thickness of the skin steels and the core polymer was 0.6 and 1 mm, respectively. Acetyl type adhesive, Loctite 401 (Henkel), was used as the adhesive between the skin and core material.

2.2 Punch test

Hemispherical punch tests were carried out to investigate the formability of the steel-polymer sandwich composites. Figure 1 shows the equipment used for this punch test. Universal testing machine (UTM) was used to conduct the punch test. A hemispherical punch was attached to upper side of UTM. The diameter of the hemispherical punch was 50 mm. Specimen-holding jig was attached to the bottom side of UTM. The diameter of cavity where the punch moved was 56.5 mm.

Figure 1. Punch test setup

Specimen was prepared with a different width varying from 10 mm to 100 mm as shown in Figure 2. Edge of these specimen was clamped by a blank-holder. The blank-holder was fixed by bolts and nuts. The beads helped specimen not to slip. Then hemispherical punch went down at a 10 mm/m forming the specimen. Punch stopped when the first failure detected. Each specimen showed a different strain path during the punch test, and resulted in different minor strain-major strain combination after failure.

Figure 2. Sandwich specimen prepared with different width: 10 mm, 20mm, 30mm, 40mm, 50mm, 100mm (from left to right)

Circle grid with 3 mm diameter was printed on the specimen with a stamp. After the punch test, the grid of curved surface was duplicated using a cellular tape to measure the diameter of the deformed grids as shown in Figure 3. Then, FLD was built by distinguishing the grids in the safe and necked area.

Figure 3. Circular grid duplicated using a cellular tape after the punch test.

2.3 Acoustic Emission test equipment

As shown in Figure 4, an acoustic emission equipment was set up to detect the delamination signal during the punch test. The wide-broad sensor was used with an operating frequency range of 10 ~1000 kHz. To minimize the noise, AE signals below 33 dB were not considered.

Figure 4: AE test setup.

2.4 Different failure modes

There are three possible failure modes during the forming of steel-polymer composites: steel fracture, polymer fracture and interfacial failure. To observe AE signal features of each failure modes, various tests were conducted. Tensile test was conducted with single steel and polymer. Lap shear test was also conducted with steel-polymer composites. As shown in Figure 5 (a) and (b), AE sensor was attached to the specimen directly. The AE signals from local necking and interfacial failure were recorded and analyzed.

Figure 5. (a) Tensile test specimen and AE sensor, (b) lap shear test specimen, (c) sensor position in punch test, (d) single steel punch test specimen, and (e) interfacial failure specimen.

Tensile test and lap shear test had two different conditions from the punch test. First, the sensor was attached directly to specimen in tensile and lap shear test. However, in punch test, there was no place to attach the sensor to specimen, so the sensor was attached to the jig for clamping the specimen (Figure 5 (c)). Second, the failure occurred in flat specimen in tensile test and lap shear test, while specimen in punch test failed in curved shape. Due to these difference, two more tests were conducted in punch test condition as shown in Figures 5 (d) and (e). AE signals from local necking and interfacial failure were recorded and analyzed.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 AE signal analysis

Stress-time curves of single steel and polymer were obtained using the tensile test. In Figure 6, AE signals from the tensile test of PA6 were synchronized with stress-time curve. The right y-axis of the graph shows the peak frequency of the signals.

Figure 6. Single polymer stress-time curve synchronized with AE signals.

As shown in Figure 6, PA6 had AE signal cluster which has frequency bands of 10~100 kHz. EG steel also had similar AE signal cluster with PA6 which has frequency bands of 10 ~ 200 kHz. Steel and polymer fracture were hardly distinguished in AE signal analysis.

Figure 7. Lap shear test of steel and steel-polymer composites specimen.

The stress-time curves of lap shear test were obtained as shown in Figure 7. A lot of AE signals

were detected compared to the tensile test of single skin and core. This seems to result from the slip between the steel and polymer during and after the delamination. The delamination between the steel and polymer core generated 2 AE signal clusters. The first cluster has peak frequency range of 10 ~ 200 kHz, and the second cluster has 300 ~ 500 kHz peak frequency bands. Interfacial failure showed different peak frequency bands compared to other two failure modes. AE events of 300 ~ 500 kHz peak frequency indicate that the delamination of steel-polymer composites occurred without question.

Single steel punch test also showed similar peak frequency band with single steel tensile test. These two tests showed same failure mode as steel, but at different test condition, indicating that system condition in the punch test did not influence peak frequency bands, i.e., only failure modes affect the peak frequency bands. Also, the lap shear test and interfacial failure in punch test showed the same peak frequency bands. Therefore, it can be claimed that the delamination during the punch test can be detected by AE equipment.

3.2 FLD based on steel fracture

The steel fracture was observed by a significant load drop during the punch test. FLD based on the steel fracture was constructed using Nakazima method. The FLD of single steel and steel-polymer composites specimen are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: FLD of single steel and steel-polymer composites specimen.

FLD of steel-polymer composites was higher than FLD of single steel. This tendency was reported by other researchers [3, 4]. This tendency is due to the thickness effect. As the material becomes thicker, the relative initial defect of the material decreases, and finally formability of the material increases [7]. When the steel went through local necking during the punch test, the strain of PA6 was small compared to the fracture strain measured from tensile test of PA6. The steel fracture always occurred prior to the polymer fracture. Therefore, the fracture of PA6 need not be considered in the FLD of steel-polymer composites.

3.3 FLD based on delamination

The delamination of steel-polymer composites can be observed by AE signals which have peak frequency of 300 ~ 500 kHz. FLD based on delamination is now being constructed and will be presented at the Conference in detail.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the formability of steel-polymer composites was investigated. To distinguish the failure modes of steel-polymer composites during the formability test, an acoustic emission technique was used. The delamination between skin steel layer and core polymer brought about unique peak frequency of AE signal. In the formability test, the steel fracture could be observed by load drop, and occurred before the polymer fracture. The FLD of steel-polymer composites based on steel fracture considering the interfacial failure such as delamination can be obtained using AE analysis.

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